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Genes of the p53 family activated during tumor suppression.

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The master tumor suppressor p53 is described as guardian of the genome resulting from its ability to protect the cell from genotoxic insults and changes in the cell cycle that de-restrict licensed cell division. Activation of p53 has transcriptional consequences with functions in the cell cycle, like activation of the *CDKN* cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor genes, as well as repressive transcriptional consequences, like silencing expression of genes that encode enzymes that catalyze nucleotide synthesis to replicate the daughter strand (DNA) to halt cell cycle progression. Separate from but related to its cellular transcriptional targets, p53 exists within a broader family of genes that belong to the p53 family that are less well-described. We measured total transcription in human cells genetically depleted of p53 to identify p53 family genes members and understand the relative changes in their quantities. We describe here genes of the p53 family activated during tumor suppression.

Results

We identified genes of the p53 family, activated by p53 during tumor suppression, by genetic depletion of p53 in human cells *in vitro*.

Figure 1: Depletion of p53 in human breast epithelial cells (MCF10A) results in silencing of *PERP*.

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n=2 MCF10A, with wild-type p53

n=1 MCF10A, with p53 shRNA

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7157	0.0113304	0.736	2.53234	1.863011	908.67	TP53	172/14517	98.8
7159	0.2356178	0.675	1.186011	0.801013	626.79	TP53BP2	1570/14517	89.2
64065	0.4315381	0.473	0.786562	0.372411	2498.59	PERP	5426/14517	62.6
378805	0.0217798	2.093	2.294187	4.801964	57.64	LINC-PINT	6136/14517	57.7
94241	0.379092	1.756	0.87957	1.544357	69.12	TP53INP1	6548/14517	54.9
55367	0.8784908	1.875	0.152883	0.28663	56.98	PIDD1	7944/14517	45.3
9537	0.6242493	2.638	0.489837	1.292366	47.71	TP53I11	8147/14517	43.9
63970	0.2016895	4.916	1.276753	6.276762	9.63	TP53AIP1	8674/14517	40.2
29965	0.9716808	4.104	0.0355	0.145677	14.14	CDIP1	10784/14517	25.7
55135	0.3837747	1.661	0.870962	1.446752	71.88	WRAP53	11423/14517	21.3
58476	0.2810557	1.688	1.077951	1.819649	73.57	TP53INP2	13330/14517	8.2
112858	0.4638073	1.356	0.732592	0.993289	114.3	TP53RK	13395/14517	7.7

Figure 2: Depletion of p53 in human breast cancer cells (MCF7) results in silencing of tumor protein p53 inducible nuclear protein 2, *TP53INP2*.

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n=3 control (MCF7; DMSO vehicle; control vector)

n=3 MCF7 (MCF7; DMSO vehicle; p53 shRNA)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
201746_at	1.01e-04	10.0642112	1.575312	3.26195527	TP53	37/54675	99.9
219370_at	3.02e-03	5.074443	-1.137456	1.52563558	RPRM	490/54675	99.9
210609_s_at	6.40e-02	2.3175089	-4.109734	0.41585233	TP53I3	5201/54675	90.5
224836_at	6.68e-02	2.2845647	-4.151706	0.55814736	TP53INP2	5389/54675	90.1
210241_s_at	8.75e-02	2.0798072	-4.412912	0.40891578	TP53TG1	6787/54675	87.6

Discussion

We identified here the salient p53 gene family members controlled by p53 in tumor suppression using a genetic loss-of-function approach in human cells.